

On the identity of *Hemimachairodus zwierzyckii* (Von Koenigswald, 1934) from Sangiran, Java, Indonesia (Mammalia, Carnivora, Machairodontinae)

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ABSTRACT

Confusion about dental morphology (viz. the upper canine serration) and taxonomy of an extinct Pleistocene sabre-tooth felid from Sangiran (Java, Indonesia) led to re-examination of its type material. Here we confirm that the taxon *Hemimachairodus* (or *Epimachairodus*) *zwierzyckii* should be rejected, being a junior synonym of *Homotherium latidens*.

Keywords Sabre-tooth, Felidae, *Homotherium latidens*, taxonomy

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INTRODUCTION

The sabre-toothed felid *Homotherium latidens* (Owen, 1846) was a top-predator having a wide distribution in time and space, i.e. the Early, Middle and Late Pleistocene and the entire northern hemisphere (Eurasia and North America), and showing large intra-specific morphological variation (Paijmans *et al.* 2017, Reumer & Van der Geer, 2026). During our research into the taxonomic status of *H. latidens* and its synonyms (Reumer & Van der Geer, 2026), doubt arose concerning the identity of a sabre-tooth cat of the classical hominid-bearing locality of Sangiran (Java, Indonesia). Jiangzuo *et al.* (2025) referred this material, originally named *Epimachairodus zwierzyckii* Von Koenigswald, 1934 and subsequently

Hemimachairodus zwierzyckii (Von Koenigswald, 1934) to *H. latidens*, but only tentatively so, leaving some doubt. A closer inspection of the material thus seemed necessary. The original material on which the name *H. zwierzyckii* was based consists of a fragmentary mandible with some dental elements still in place, and a broken and partly restored upper canine (C sup.). Both the description of the material and the illustrations provided by Von Koenigswald (1934, 1940, 1974) seem inadequate. In order to clarify the situation and to properly identify the material, we re-examined the type fossil and provide an adequate description.

SYSTEMATIC PALAEOLOGY

Order Carnivora Bowdich, 1821

Family Felidae Fischer von Waldheim, 1817

Subfamily Machairodontidae Gill, 1872

Genus *Homotherium* Fabrini, 1890

Homotherium latidens (Owen, 1846) (*nomen protectum*)

Relevant synonymy

Epimachairodus zwierzyckii Von Koenigswald, 1934

Epimachairodus zwierzyckii Von Koenigswald, 1934 in: Von Koenigswald, 1940

Homotherium zwierzyckii (Koenigswald) in: Kurtén, 1962

Hemimachairodus zwierzyckii (Von Koenigswald) in: Von Koenigswald, 1974

Homotherium ultimum (Teilhard de Chardin) in: Von Koenigswald, 1974

"*Homotherium zwierzyckii*" in: Aimi & Aziz, 1985

Homotherium latidens (Owen, 1846) in: Jiangzuo *et al.*, 2025 ('tentatively')

Referred material

A left mandible with broken i2, broken i3, c inf. and p4, no. K147 (used as the holotype specimen of the taxon *Epimachairodus zwierzyckii*), and a reconstructed left C sup., both of Sangiran (Java, Indonesia), Museum Geologi Bandung (MGB). For measurements see Von Koenigswald (1974).

DISCUSSION

Von Koenigswald (1934) described and depicted a fragmentary mandible of a sabre-tooth felid from the Early Pleistocene black clays of the Sangiran (Pucangan) Formation at the Glagah Ombo Site, Sangiran, central Java (see Figure 1A) and gave it the new name *Epimachairodus zwierzyckii*. A formal diagnosis was not provided, but a detailed description of the specimen in the German language may be regarded as such. Relevant are the following (translated) observations. Of the incisors, of which only the roots are preserved, i1 is the smallest. The damaged lower canine was relatively small; its mesial edge shows a distinct serration, its distal edge is damaged. A diastema of 46 mm length separates the canine from p4. There is no p3 indicating a highly specialized specimen. Also p4 is not entirely preserved. Its protoconid shows a serration on both edges, finer on the distal edge.

The initial observation of serrations on both sides of the protoconid of p4 is relevant here, although now only the serrations on the anterior (mesial) edge are still observable due to damage (see Figure 2). Von Koenigswald (1934) then concludes that the strong serration, the small canine and the absence of p3 indicates a representative of the genus *Epimachairodus*, to which genus he also reckons *E. latidens*, now *Homotherium latidens*. It is noteworthy that Von Koenigswald (1934) does not mention the presence of an upper canine. Von Koenigswald (1940), in an overview of hominin remains

Figure 1 Holotype mandible MGB K147 as depicted by Von Koenigswald, 1934 (A); the same as depicted in Von Koenigswald, 1940 (B); reconstruction drawing of the holotype specimen with the addition of the ramus fragment with p4 and m1, from Von Koenigswald, 1974 (C); reconstruction drawing of the upper canine, from Von Koenigswald, 1974 (D).

Figure 2 The p4 in lingual view. Serrations on the anterior (mesial) edge of the tooth are indicated.

from Java and their accompanying faunal elements, mentions *Epimachairodus zwierzyckii* and depicts the same specimen (see Figure 1B).

Kurtén (1962) then discusses Von Koenigswald's (1934) *E. zwierzyckii* holotype specimen in a paper dedicated to a highly damaged machairodontine canine root from the classic locality of Trinil (Java, Indonesia). He writes: "(...) there can be no doubt of the homotheriine affinities of the form described from the Djétis by von Koenigswald (1934). This is based on a fragment of the lower jaw, containing the damaged incisors, the canine, and the fourth premolar. The large but very thin p4, the serrated edges of the canine, and the shape of the jaw demonstrate that this specimen is a member of the group variously known under the names *Homotherium*, *Dinobastis*, and *Epimachairodus*. The last-mentioned name is a junior synonym and may be disregarded." (end of citation). Kurtén (1962, fig.1) depicts three upper canines in his paper: the damaged and crown-less root from Trinil, a *Megantereon megantereon* canine from Val d'Arno, Italy with an unserrated crown, and a canine of *Homotherium crenatidens* (= *H. latidens*), also from Val d'Arno; the latter showing distinctly serrated mesial and distal edges which is a characteristic for homotheriines.

Von Koenigswald (1974) increased the confusion by creating a new genus *Hemimachairodus* for the Sangiran material. The material available to Von Koenigswald was augmented by a fragmentary piece of a right mandibular ramus that was described as follows: "In our additional specimen, like the type specimen from Sangiran, the jaw is broken about 1 cm behind the molar and 2 cm in front of the premolar; the lower border of the jaw has not been preserved." The

specimen (coll. Senckenberg Museum Frankfurt SMF/PA/F 6679) only consists of a small fragment of the ramus with two dental elements preserved: p4 and m1 (Von Koenigswald 1974, plate 1a, 2a; see also Jiangzuo *et al.* 2025, fig. 4b). *Hemimachairodus* was diagnosed with the following characteristics: "Differs from *Homotherium* s.str. by the complete reduction of the third lower premolar (as in *Smilodon*) and the limitation of the serration of the upper canine to the posterior cutting edge." (Von Koenigswald, 1974, p. 267). Both diagnostics are erroneous.

First, the presence or absence of a p3 cannot be used as a diagnostic feature, as this feature is variable. Some specimens of *Homotherium* do have a p3, such as for example the Dutch North Sea specimen (Reumer *et al.* 2003), a mandible from Tennessee, USA (Rawn-Schatzinger & Collins 1981) and a mandible from Perrier, France (De Bonis 1976), while some do not (e.g., the British Kessingland specimen, Backhouse, 1886). Jiangzuo *et al.* (2025, p. 29) also noted that p3 is 'sometime lost'. Second, limitation of serration to the posterior (distal) edge of the canine and its absence on the anterior (mesial) edge is not observed. *Megantereon* is a sabre-tooth cat with unserrated canines, *Homotherium* has serration on both edges of the canine (see also De Vos & Aziz 1987). Canines with serration on only one side of the tooth are unknown, contrary to the remark of Von Koenigswald (1974, p. 269). Also the p4 has serrations on both the mesial and the distal edge, as already observed by Von Koenigswald (1934), even though they are presently indistinguishable on the distal edge due to damage.

Figure 1C shows Von Koenigswald's (1974) reconstruction

Figure 3 The holotype specimen with the reconstructed upper canine, as on display at the Museum Geologi, Bandung, Indonesia.

of the mandible, drawn by artificially combining the 1934 holotype specimen and the 1974 mandibular fragment with p4 and m3. Figure 1D shows a similarly made reconstruction of the upper canine, with serrations on the concave posterior (distal) side only. Von Koenigswald (1974, p.268) mentions the presence of two fragments in the collection from Sangiran.

He wrote: "We have fragments of two flat upper canines. One fragment, 61,5 mm long and 12,8 mm thick consists mainly of the root part of the tooth, the other 54 mm long and at the upper end 25 mm, at the lower end 21 mm wide, only of the blade. The posterior surface is rolled, but on the anterior side a sharp keel is present, which does not shows any traces of

Figure 4 The reconstructed upper canine in lingual view (A), buccal view (B), posterior (distal) view (C), and anterior (mesial) view (D). Both edges show serrations.

serration. In spite of that this, however is not the caninus of a *Megantereon* (for which non-serrated canines are typical) where this tooth is more slender and elongated. The two fragments of the upper canine can be used for a reconstruction." (end of citation). In the same paper, Von Koenigswald (1974, p. 268) mentions another canine from Sangiran: "A more complete upper canine from Sangiran is in the collections of the Geological Survey of Indonesia in Bandung. If my recollection is right – I have seen the tooth before the war – that tooth is broader and shorter, more like *Homotherium crenatidens* (...) and might belong to the second species described in this paper." (end of citation). This 'second species' is *Homotherium ultimum* (see below). If he had seen this canine before the war, his recollection must date from at least 35 years earlier.

We cannot but conclude that the erection of the genus *Hemimachairodus* is based on erroneous suppositions. Figure 3 shows the material as it is presently available at the Museum Geologi in Bandung. It concerns the holotype mandible of the taxon *Epimachairodus zwierzyckii* and an upper canine. This tooth is a reconstruction, most probably of the two fragments that were used to make the reconstruction mentioned by Von Koenigswald (1974, p. 268, fig. 2; our Figure 1D). Photographs of the canine (Figure 4) clearly show serrations on both the mesial and distal edges of the crown, unmistakably identifying it as a *Homotherium*. *Epimachairodus zwierzyckii* Von Koenigswald, 1934 and *Hemimachairodus zwierzyckii* (Von Koenigswald, 1934) are thus junior synonyms of *Homotherium latidens* (Owen, 1846); see Reumer & Van der Geer (2026) for further synonymies.

In his last paper, Von Koenigswald (1974) introduced yet another *Homotherium* from Sangiran. It concerns a right mandibular ramus with four elements: c, p3, p4 and m1 (coll. Senckenberg Museum Frankfurt SMF/PA/F 6676) and possibly the canine seen before the war. It was identified as *Homotherium ultimum* (Teilhard de Chardin) and the material (but not the canine) was depicted as a drawing (Von Koenigswald 1974, Plate 1b, 2b) together with the *Hemimachairodus zwierzyckii* fragment with p4 and m1 (l.c., Plate 1a, 2a), and recently as a photograph by Jiangzuo *et al.* (2025, fig. 4a). The difference between the taxa is the presence of a p3 in *Ho. ultimum* while this element is absent in *He. zwierzyckii*; the size differences of p4 and m1, as can be deduced from Von Koenigswald's (1974) illustrations where both specimens are shown in 'actual size', however, are negligible. As the presence or absence of p3 is not diagnostic, as already mentioned above, *Homotherium ultimum* is a junior synonym of *H. latidens* (see Reumer & Van der Geer 2026), and there is thus no reason to suppose that two closely related machairodontines occurred simultaneously in Sangiran.

Megantereon was also present in the Pleistocene of Java. Kurtén (1962) published the root fragment from Trinil mentioned above, and De Vos & Aziz (1987) subsequently published two rather similarly looking upper canines of Sangiran; additional cheek teeth were described by Jiangzuo *et al.* (2025). This implies the presence of two species of top-predator felines with sabre-teeth in the Javanese Pleistocene, a

meganterine and a machairodontine: *Megantereon* sp. and *Homotherium latidens*.

CONCLUSION

The Pleistocene sabre-tooth felids known from Sangiran (Java, Indonesia) belong to two taxa, a meganterine and a machairodontine: *Megantereon* sp. and *Homotherium latidens*. We are thus able to confirm the tentative taxonomic conclusion of Jiangzuo *et al.* (2025). Earlier named taxa *Epimachairodus zwierzyckii* Von Koenigswald, 1934, *Hemimachairodus zwierzyckii* (Von Koenigswald, 1934), and *Homotherium ultimum* (Teilhard de Chardin, 1936) are junior synonyms of *H. latidens* (Owen, 1846).

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